

E-LEARNING: ISSUES AND CHALLENGES OF IN INDIAN EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

The study in E-learning: Issues and Challenges of in Indian Education institutions of higher education, the issue of utilizing modern information and communication technologies for teaching and learning is very important. E-learning involves the use of digital tools for teaching and learning in education. It makes use of technological tools to enable learners study anytime and anywhere. It involves the training, delivery of knowledge and motivates students to interact with each other, as well as exchange and respect different point of views. It eases communication and improves the relationships that sustain learning. Despite some challenges discussed, the literature has sought to explain the role of e-learning in particular and how e-Learning has made a strong impact in teaching and learning in Indian education system. Its adoption in some institutions has increased faculty and learner's access to information and has provided a rich environment for collaboration among students which have improved academic standards. The overall literature which explains the advantages and disadvantages of e-learning suggests the need for its implementation in Indian education for faculty, administrators and students to enjoy the full benefits that come with its adoption and implementation.

INTRODUCTION

E-learning is the use of ICT to deliver education and training to learners (Sun et al., 2008). ICTs that is used effectively by instructors and learners have the potential to make education more accessible and improve the quality of the education (UNESCO, 2007).

Stockley (2005) defines E-Learning as “the delivery of a learning, training or education program by electronic means, e-learning involves the use of a computer or electronic device (e.g. a mobile phone) to provide training, educational or learning material”.

Oblinger and Hawkins (2005) suggest that e-learning “has morphed from a fully-online course to the use of technology to deliver some or all of a course independent of fixed time and place..... Students can be residential, commuting or at a distance”.

It can be noticed that most of these definitions focus on the means used to provide e-learning rather than the process of learning itself. This realization might have reduced the scope that e-learning as a concept is really covering. The scope of the term e-learning in terms of delivery involves the use of any kind of electronic equipment's to present learning content, but in terms of objectives it should involve the implementation of learning.

Mason and Rennie (2006) included an e-learning definition produced by Open and Distance Learning Quality Council, UK which is for the first time distinct between the content of learning and the process. "E-Learning is the effective learning process created by combining digitally delivered content with (learning) support and services".

Benefits/Advantage of e-Learning:

A multi-billion dollar industry does not spring to fame without an amazing array of benefits tagging along, which make the millions all the more worthwhile. Let's have a look at some of them.

Benefits of e- learning

- Cost effective and time saving
- Higher knowledge retention
- Room for discretion
- Large target audience base
- Easy course tracking
- Encourages sharing

1) Cost cutting: Investing in E-learning infrastructure and technology is one time investment for stakeholders and regular up gradation & maintenance is required. Time saving: It saves time of instructor as well as learners by accessing the information from anywhere. Development in Knowledge: It helps in developing new theories or practices due to participation of multiple learners and instructors from various places. Social Cause: Education Institute or Instructor can distribute n number of copies of modules or software to learners free of cost as a social responsibility. In country like India many NGO's are already practicing such modules under Right To Education Policy. Environment Protecting: Proper use of devices and technology replacing paper and other resources of learning which were manufactured by companies.

2) Developing New Knowledge Facilities for e-learning: E-learning environment needs to support the rapid increase in the size and variety of data by appropriate semantic services. The semantic services generate a surrounding semantic context for learning support. Research that needs to work on: Development of learning and reasoning theories for uncertain and incomplete knowledge. Support for the development of large-scale learning facilities. Support for a dynamic learning process. Support for information sharing across different learning

facilities. Developments of lightweight knowledge capture technique for promotion of lifelong learning.

- 3) Research Issues for e-learning: Current e-learning research brings together pedagogical, technical and organizational concerns within a wider set of socio-cultural factors. These factors influence the research agenda in e-learning system. Understanding these broader social and cultural issues is of significant importance to the research communities involved in e-learning and will have a significant role in informing future practices
- 4) It is a very efficient way of delivering courses online.
- 5) Due to its convenience and flexibility, the resources are available from anywhere and at any time.
- 6) Everyone, who are part time students or are working full time, can take advantage of web-based learning.

Disadvantages of E-learning:

- 1) Cost and Knowhow: While delivery costs of e-learning are significantly reduced compared to costs associated with classroom learning delivery, especially when large numbers of learners are involved (RUMBLE, 2001). The initial development and purchase of e-learning products represents a major barrier to the adoption of e-learning training within organizations. This claim is substantiated by evidence from a survey conducted for the Office of Learning Technologies (OLT) in Canada, which found that cost was the single most important factor preventing employers from investing in e-learning (DUGAS; GREEN; LECKIE, 1999). In any case, organization must weigh the initial costs of developing e-learning against savings accrued from economics of scale at delivery time.
- 2) Lack of time: The lack of time as an obstructing factor comes second, after the cost barrier. Long development cycles prohibit many institutions from engaging in production of custom e-learning training. Lengthy time-to-promote is especially true for small institutions who have limited capacities to produce complex, media-rich, highly interactive and customized solutions. As a result, an increasing number of institutions are starting to outsource their e-learning activities to an application service provider (HAMBRECHT et al., 2000). The trend toward the ASP model is still very slow mainly because institutions have proprietary content, highly confidential in nature, which they want to protect.
- 3) Cyber Crime: There are chances of unethical hacking of confidential information and putting unwanted virus or information on instructor and learner's portal or devices.

4) **Technological Barriers:** Severe limitations of technology infrastructure also serve to hamper enthusiasm and the widespread use of e-learning technologies. These restrictions range from inadequate network speed and bandwidth capacity to incompatibility across different platforms and between different content materials. The bandwidth refers to the capacity of a communication channel to carry information (e.g., text, graphics, audio and videos). The insufficient bandwidth was rated as the most significant barrier in a survey where 65% of those surveyed indicated that increased transfer speed would result in increased usage for them. On a positive note, software, hardware incompatibility and low bandwidth are poised to improve rapidly as standards for interoperability are being developed.

5) **E-learning and Illiterate Population:**

As per Census Report 2011 published by Government of India:

Table 1. Percentage of Literate Population

Year	Literates (% of total population)	Illiterates (% of total population)
2001	65%	35%
2011	74%	26%

Source: Annual Report 2013-14, published by Ministry of HRD GOI.

The above Table 1 shows that the percentage of literate population in the total population has increased in 2011, from 65% to 74%, similarly, the percentage of illiterate population has decreased from 35% to 26% in the span of a decade. Still the fact remains that 26% of India's total population is still illiterate and e-learning can prove helpful to reduce the illiteracy as the advancement in technology and communication has made teaching and training possible anywhere, anytime. The Learner can learn anywhere; i.e. outside the boundaries of formal classroom. It will be very effective in case of adult education and training. It is a very powerful medium for pre-primary and primary education as it is in audio visual form and can attract even the school dropouts. It will be very effective in case of adult education and training.

6) **Limited Social Interaction:** There is a limited opportunity to interact face-to-face with professors and other students. Especially in self-paced courses – difficult to develop relationships with classmates. Possibility of limited local networking opportunities. Most of the communication through email, chat room or discussion groups, but no offline get together. No personalized attentions from instructor with regards to face-to face interactions and feedbacks. No campus atmosphere to create social interaction.

- 7) Technological Challenges: The e-learning raises significant challenges in the technological research area. For development of e-learning resources that meet the users requirement need to be addressed.
- 8) Most of the online assessments are limited to questions that are only objective in nature.
- 9) There is also the problem of the extent of security of online learning programs.
- 10) The authenticity of a particular student's work is also a problem as online just about anyone can do a project rather than the actual student itself.
- 11) The assessments that are computer marked generally have a tendency of being only knowledge-based and not necessarily practicality-based'.

CONCLUSION

E-learning involves the use of digital tools for teaching and learning in education. It makes use of technological tools to enable learners study anytime and anywhere. It involves the training, delivery of knowledge and motivates students to interact with each other, as well as exchange and respect different point of views. It eases communication and improves the relationships that sustain learning. Despite some challenges discussed, the literature has sought to explain the role of e-learning in particular and how e-Learning has made a strong impact in teaching and learning in Indian education system. Its adoption in some institutions has increased faculty and learner's access to information and has provided a rich environment for collaboration among students which have improved academic standards. The overall literature which explains the advantages and disadvantages of e-learning suggests the need for its implementation in Indian education for faculty, administrators and students to enjoy the full benefits that come with its adoption and implementation.

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